

NEA Initiatives for the Back End of Innovative Reactor Systems

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ABSTRACT

The Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) has launched several initiatives to advance understanding and solutions for the back end of innovative reactor systems, including small modular reactors and Generation IV technologies, recognising this as a critical element for their responsible and sustainable deployment. A key effort in this area has been the Focus Group on the Back End of Advanced Reactors (FG-BEAR), which operated between July 2024 and February 2025. The group identified key gaps and needs across technical, economic, societal and regulatory dimensions and developed recommendations for a comprehensive approach to address back-end challenges for these new designs. Additionally, the NEA joint project on Waste Integration for Small and Advanced Reactor Designs (WISARD) was launched in May 2025. WISARD addresses critical technical areas such as used fuel and waste characterisation, treatment and recycling, storage, transport, and disposal – focusing on selected systems and fuels relevant to its members. Finally, recent developments in the global nuclear energy landscape further highlight the strategic importance of revitalising approaches to used fuel recycling and back-end management. Together, these initiatives highlight pathways and strategies to support emerging nuclear technologies.

Keywords: SMR, Generation IV, nuclear fuel cycle, radioactive waste management, recycling

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) brings together 34 member countries across Europe, North America, and the Asia-Pacific region, collectively representing more than 80% of the world's installed nuclear capacity. NEA activities are organised through eight standing technical committees and numerous working bodies that engage senior officials and experts from member countries in addressing all aspects of civil nuclear energy.

Among these committees, the Radioactive Waste Management Committee (RWMC) and the Committee on Decommissioning of Nuclear Installations and Legacy Management (CDLM) focus on the back end of nuclear fuel cycles. Their work takes a holistic approach, integrating environmental and operational safety, economic considerations, societal impacts, and regulatory frameworks to support safe, efficient, and socially acceptable solutions.

As countries increasingly turn to nuclear to strengthen energy security and meet climate goals, small modular reactors (SMRs) and Generation IV technologies are expected to play pivotal roles in the evolving energy landscape. These innovative designs often differ substantially from current reactor types, in terms of fuel, coolant and recycling options, as well as in their potential locations and applications [1]. Such specific features are expected to generate new spent fuels and waste streams, with implications on all stages of radioactive waste management – including storage, transport and disposal – as well as decommissioning operations.

Recognising the importance of anticipating these challenges, the NEA has launched targeted initiatives to explore the back-end implications of these emerging technologies. Initial efforts included

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international workshops held in 2022 and 2023 [2-3], followed by topical sessions during the CDLM and RWMC annual meetings in 2024 [4-5]. The activities have provided valuable insights into emerging challenges and opportunities in this rapidly evolving field.

This paper presents recent and ongoing NEA initiatives in this area, notably the Focus Group on the Back End of Advanced Reactors (FG-BEAR), the NEA joint project on Waste Integration for Small and Advanced Reactor Designs (WISARD), and recent work on nuclear fuel recycling. These activities are complementary: FG-BEAR focused on identifying gaps and recommendations for the back end of advanced reactors; WISARD assesses how advanced reactor fuels, materials, and design choices impact the back end of the nuclear fuel cycle for selected systems and fuels; and the recycling initiatives consider broader implications for sustainable nuclear fuel management. Together, they highlight pathways and strategies to support emerging nuclear technologies and provide member countries with a common technical basis and strategic guidance to inform future national and international activities, including planning, R&D prioritisation, and regulatory discussions.

2. FOCUS GROUP ON THE BACK END OF ADVANCED REACTORS (FG-BEAR)

Building on prior work, the RWMC and CDLM decided in March 2024 to establish the FG-BEAR. Its goals was to develop a comprehensive understanding of the unique features and challenges associated with the back-end management for SMRs and Generation IV systems and to identify areas requiring future consideration. The group brought together twelve members from eleven member countries and operated from July 2024 to February 2025. It reviewed ongoing and planned work, defined six key topic areas each containing three interrelated sub-areas (see Figure 1) and assessed the state of the art to identify gaps and needs for each one of them.

Figure 1. Topic areas of interest considered by the FG-BEAR (source: NEA [6])

The findings were presented at the 7th Joint Session of the CDLM and RWMC in February 2025 [6]. Based on the analysis, ten focus areas were identified for further consideration by the committees and the wider NEA community (see Figure 2). These do not represent a ranking or prioritisation but provide a foundation for future activities.

Figure 2. Key areas for further consideration for the back end of advanced reactors (source: NEA [6])

Decommissioning by design: Early integration of decommissioning considerations into reactor design was identified as a major opportunity to improve safety, efficiency, and cost control. The group highlighted the importance of linking dismantling scenarios to initial decommissioning plans and aligning these with waste management strategies from the beginning.

Novel locations: SMRs and advanced reactors may be deployed in diverse environment, including remote, industrial, urban, and maritime settings, each presenting specific logistical and safety challenges. Back-end management strategies will need to be tailored to site conditions, with flexible infrastructure and regulatory frameworks to accommodate location-specific constraints.

Innovative technologies: Advances in digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics, and digital twins can significantly enhance back-end operations. Automation and AI-driven tools can increase operational efficiency and worker safety, while digital twins support lifecycle tracking and predictive maintenance. Advanced monitoring systems and robotic tools can improve precision in waste characterisation and treatment.

Materials and fuel characterisation: Comprehensive data on new fuels, coolants, and structural materials are essential to ensure safe handling and disposal. The group identified a need to strengthen experimental and modelling capabilities to support radionuclide inventory calculations, criticality modelling, and the behaviour of unconventional waste forms like graphite, salts, and liquid metals.

Compatibility with existing back-end solutions: Ensuring that new waste types and materials are compatible with existing storage, transport, treatment, recycling, and disposal systems is critical. The group noted the potential value of developing modular treatment units for SMR waste and the need to assess the regulatory acceptability of new fuels and materials within established frameworks.

Opportunities for "game changers": Circular-economy approaches and international collaboration were recognised as potential "game changers." Advances in recycling technologies, harmonised global policies, and expanded nuclear materials markets could enable waste minimisation and resource recovery across reactor types. These developments require coordinated policy and regulatory innovation to support implementation.

Back-end financing schemes: Financial planning is central to sustainable back-end management. The group underlined the need to address uncertainties in cost estimation for advanced fuel cycles, identify funding mechanisms for new treatment and storage facilities, and support long-term investment strategies to ensure financial resilience over the lifecycle of these technologies.

Cost estimation and optimisation: Accurate and transparent cost assessments are needed to support decision-making and public trust. The analysis found that it will be necessary to determine whether SMR-specific cost-assessment methodologies are required. It will also be important to evaluate waste management costs across reactor designs and to assess the economic feasibility of extending existing storage facilities versus constructing new ones.

Workforce needs and skills development: A qualified and adaptable workforce will be essential to implement advanced back-end solutions. The group noted that SMRs and Generation IV technologies will require new competencies in waste management, digital tools, and decommissioning operations. Long-term education, training, and international cooperation programmes are needed to build and maintain these capabilities.

Coordination across the value chain: Effective coordination among all stakeholders (reactor designers, radioactive waste management organisations, regulators, research bodies, and the public) is key to success. Early and continuous coordination can help address public concerns about SMR waste and ensure that back-end considerations are integrated into reactor design and policy decisions.

Key priorities identified by the CDLM and RWMC include advancing decommissioning by design, ensuring compatibility with existing back-end solutions, and undertaking cost estimations. The committees are now working to define next steps to address these priority areas.

3. NEA WISARD JOINT PROJECT

Another major NEA initiative is the joint project on Waste Integration for Small and Advanced Reactor Designs (WISARD), officially launched in May 2025 after a preparatory year of workshop and meetings to define its scope. In accordance with Article 5 of the OECD Statute, NEA joint projects operate as self-contained international undertakings (distinct from the committee-based activities), funded and governed by participating organisations, with results accessible only to them.

WISARD represents the first coordinated international effort to systematically assess how fuels, coolants, materials, and design features of advanced reactors affect the back end of the nuclear fuel cycle. Its programme of work is organised into six interlinked tasks, covering the full range of waste management areas and culminating in an integrated assessment:

- Task 1: Irradiated fuel and coolant characterisation
- Task 2: Treatment and recycling
- Task 3: Storage
- Task 4: Transportation
- Task 5: Disposal (deep geological repositories and boreholes)
- Task 6: Cross-cutting integration and interdependencies.

Running from 2025 to 2028, WISARD brings together twelve signatories across Asia, Europe and North America, including national laboratories, research institutes, reactor developers, and industry players. Multiple third parties also contribute to implementing the programme of work.

The project evaluates used fuel and waste from a variety of SMR and advanced reactor systems, including molten salt reactors (MSRs), TRISO-fuelled high temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs), sodium- and lead-cooled fast reactors (SFRs and LFRs), and light-water reactor SMR designs. The overarching objective is to assess the compatibility of new spent fuel and waste streams with existing back-end pathways and to identify where innovation may be required to ensure compatibility in the future.

By addressing spent-fuel and waste issues early in the design phase, WISARD underscores the increasing importance of planning for the full lifecycle of emerging nuclear technologies. Its result will help avoid unnecessary future costs and to support long-term sustainability of innovative systems.

4. RECYCLING INITIATIVES

Recent developments in the global nuclear energy landscape have underscored the strategic importance of revitalising approaches to used fuel recycling. In response, the NEA has launched targeted initiatives to support informed policy development. In 2024 and 2025, the NEA organised dedicated sessions at

the *Roadmaps to New Nuclear* Ministerial Conferences, bringing together senior representatives from research organisations, industry, government agencies, and national waste management organisations.

The first session, “*Waste Management, Recycling and the Future of the Nuclear Fuel Cycle*”, examined the challenges and opportunities associated with fuel recycling in the context of an anticipated tripling of nuclear capacity. Participants expressed strong interest in reprocessing and recycling as a means of optimising resource use and strengthen waste management strategies and reaffirmed the NEA’s critical role in providing policy guidance and fostering international cooperation.

A second session, “*Closing the Nuclear Fuel Cycle – Drivers and Challenges*”, explored how renewed interest in nuclear energy – including significant investment in both large-scale Generation III reactors and innovative technologies – is reshaping expectations for the nuclear fuel cycle. Participants noted that recycling offers promising pathways for both the front and back ends of the fuel cycle, while deep geological repositories remain essential for the disposal of ultimate waste. The session underscored the need for early engagement with regulators and international partners, standardisation of fuels and facilities, and the integration of waste-minimisation principles into reactor and fuel-cycle design. They also stressed the importance of stepwise research and developments and demonstration (RD&D) programmes, robust economic models to underpin investment, and transparent dialogue with the public and stakeholders to build and maintain trust.

Complementing these high-level exchanges, the NEA has recently published a paper entitled “*Recycling: A Key Enabler for Sustainable Nuclear Fuel Cycles*”. The document provides accessible, high-level insights for policymakers and stakeholders, recognising the diverse levels of technical, political, and regulatory understanding associated with recycling technologies. It outlines the role of recycling, strategic options and benefits, alongside legal and regulatory considerations, infrastructure and economic requirements, and the implications for waste management, including the optimisation of deep geological repositories. The paper stresses that realising the full potential of nuclear fuel recycling will require forward-looking policies, supportive regulatory frameworks, and targeted investment. It presents **strategic requirements** to guide government decision-making, together with **enabling actions** to support effective implementation (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. *Recycling: Strategic requirements and enabling actions* (source: NEA [7])

Key messages include the role of recycling in enhancing natural resource efficiency, reinforcing intergenerational responsibility, and contributing to the overall sustainability of nuclear energy, achieved in line of safety, security, and non-proliferation commitments. Established technologies already provide a solid foundation for current and near-term recycling efforts, while continued

research will further expand future capabilities. Decisions taken today will shape the structure, sustainability, and resilience of tomorrow's nuclear fuel cycles.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The evolving landscape of nuclear energy, marked by the deployment of small modular reactors and Generation IV technologies, presents both opportunities and challenges for the back-end management of nuclear fuel. As highlighted in this paper, addressing these challenges requires not only technical innovation but also coordinated planning across the entire fuel cycle. NEA initiatives such as the Focus Group on the Back End of Advanced Reactors (FG-BEAR) and the WISARD project exemplify the value of structured international collaboration, bringing together experts, regulators, and industry stakeholders from multiple countries to identify key gaps and needs and develop forward-looking solutions.

Moreover, the agency's work on recycling highlights the strategic value of shared learning and policy guidance, ensuring that advancements in reactor technologies are complemented by safe, socially acceptable, and resilient solutions for spent fuel and radioactive waste.

Together, these initiatives provide member countries with a common technical basis and strategic orientation to inform planning, R&D prioritisation, and regulatory discussions at national and international levels. In doing so, they establish a robust foundation for the responsible deployment of advanced nuclear systems, reinforcing global nuclear sustainability and demonstrating how collaborative foresight can transform the complex challenges of the nuclear back end into opportunities for progress.

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